

Incommensurate fractional recurrent neural networks

Babak Shiri^a, Zahra Alijani^{b,*}, Ioannis Dassios^c, Dumitru Baleanu^{d,e}

^a Key Laboratory of Numerical Simulation of Sichuan Provincial Universities, School of Mathematics and Big Data, Neijiang Normal University, Neijiang, 641100, China

^b Institute for Research and Applications of Fuzzy Modeling, University of Ostrava, 30. dubna 22, Ostrava, 701 03, Czech Republic

^c Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

^d Department of Computer Science and Mathematics, Lebanese American University, Beirut, 1102 2801, Lebanon

^e Institute of Space Sciences, Magurele-Bucharest, R 76900, Romania

HIGHLIGHTS

- **Innovative FRNN Design:** FRNNs inspired by IFDSs utilize diverse fractional orders to model complex and heterogeneous temporal dynamics.
- **Gradient Computation Solution:** A forward-forward recursive method resolves the limitations of back-propagation in FRNNs.
- **Robust Training Approach:** Mini-batch SGD combined with ADAM effectively tunes weights, biases, and the fractional memory vector $\vec{\alpha}$.
- **Strong Empirical Results:** FRNNs perform well on time-series tasks, reducing MSE and maintaining stable $\vec{\alpha}$ ordering.
- **Cross-Disciplinary Integration:** Bridges fractional calculus and artificial intelligence to capture.

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a novel class of neural networks called **Incommensurate Fractional Recurrent Neural Networks (FRNNs)**, inspired by incommensurate fractional difference systems. Unlike classical RNNs, FRNNs incorporate learnable fractional orders to capture heterogeneous temporal dependencies. To address the failure of back-propagation caused by cross-layer and cross-time coupling, we propose a **forward-forward recursive gradient computation method** combined with mini-batch SGD and ADAM optimization. Extensive experiments on multiple time-series datasets, including synthetic sinusoidal sequences, chaotic sequences, and real-world financial and energy data, demonstrate that FRNN achieves lower prediction error compared to RNNs. These results confirm the effectiveness of fractional memory dynamics for sequential data processing.

1. Introduction

Incommensurate fractional differential and difference systems (IFDSs) have attracted considerable interest in recent years due to their ability to model a wide range of complex dynamical behaviors. Unlike commensurate systems, where all components evolve under the same fractional order, incommensurate systems are governed by distinct fractional orders, enabling more flexible and nuanced representations of heterogeneous dynamics.

Despite their modeling advantages, IFDSs have limitations. As noted in [13], one significant drawback is their potential to violate conservation laws, making them less suitable for systems requiring strict conservation of mass, energy, or momentum. However, in practical domains such as epidemiology, biology, engineering, astronomy, and signal

processing—where conservation principles are often approximations—IFDSs have demonstrated superior realism and accuracy [2,7,11,12,15,19]. In neuroscience, fractional-order models have been employed to better capture the electromechanical behavior of neurons. While the classical Hodgkin-Huxley model remains a foundational framework, Drapaca [14] proposed a fractional-order model that integrates mechanical and electrochemical activities in the brain. This has inspired further research into incommensurate fractional differential equations (IFDEs) for neural systems. For instance, Brandibur and Kaslik [5,6] explored nonlinear dynamics, Ramadoss et al. [21] studied chimera states in fractional FitzHugh-Nagumo neurons, and Cao et al. [8] developed adaptive control strategies for neural networks using IFDEs. Memristor-based neural networks (MNNs) offer another promising application, where memristors replace traditional resistive components to better emulate

* Corresponding author.

Email addresses: shiri@njtc.edu.cn (B. Shiri), Zahra.Alijani@osu.cz (Z. Alijani), idasios@auth.gr (I. Dassios), dumitru.baleanu@lau.edu.lb (D. Baleanu).

synaptic behavior. MNNs are particularly effective in modeling cognitive functions such as associative memory. Recent work, such as [17], has investigated synchronization properties of delayed IFDEs within MNN architectures.

From a computational standpoint, discrete-time models are especially valuable. In many nonlinear discrete systems, recursive solution schemes can bypass the need for classical existence and uniqueness theorems. However, research on discrete incommensurate systems remains limited. For example, Abbes et al. [1] proposed a macroeconomic model based on incommensurate fractional differences, Al-Taani et al. [3] introduced a discrete memristive neural model, and [23] examined the stability of nonlinear incommensurate fractional difference systems. Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are a natural class of discrete-time systems widely used for sequential data tasks such as speech recognition, text generation, and time-series forecasting. Popular RNN architectures include long short-term memory (LSTM) networks, gated recurrent units (GRUs), Hopfield networks, Elman networks, and Jordan networks. For a comprehensive overview, see *Deep Learning* by Goodfellow, Bengio, and Courville [16]. Classical RNNs are typically defined as:

$$\vec{o}(t) = \vec{f}(\vec{i}(t), \vec{o}(t-1)), \quad (1)$$

where $\vec{i}(t) = [i_1(t), \dots, i_v(t)]^T : \mathbb{N}_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^v$ is the input sequence, $\vec{o}(t) = [o_1(t), \dots, o_\mu(t)]^T : \mathbb{N}_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^\mu$ is the output sequence, and $\vec{f} = [f_1, \dots, f_\mu] : \mathbb{R}^v \times \mathbb{R}^\mu \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^\mu$ is a parameterized function.

To overcome the limitations of fixed memory depth in classical RNNs and uniform fractional orders in commensurate fractional models, we propose an **incommensurate fractional recurrent neural network (FRNN)** that integrates nabla fractional difference operators with learnable fractional orders. FRNNs are built on incommensurate fractional dynamics, which introduce *cross-layer and cross-time parameter coupling* (Section 4 of the manuscript). For time steps $t > 1$, the output $\vec{o}(t)$ depends on past outputs (e.g., $\vec{o}(t-1)$), which are themselves functions of weights from all layers—including subsequent layers relative to the current computation. BP relies on the sequential dependency of neural network layers, where each layer’s parameters only influence subsequent layers in the forward pass. This assumption is directly violated by FRNNs’ temporal recurrence and cross-layer coupling, leading to unresolvable gradient ambiguity. Consequently, BP cannot be computationally implemented for FRNNs, as it fails to propagate error signals consistently through the network’s temporal and layer-wise dependencies.

The proposed forward-forward recursive method is not designed to outperform BP, but rather to address the inherent infeasibility of BP for FRNNs. By leveraging the FRNN’s temporal recurrence to compute gradients in the forward pass, this method resolves the cross-layer and cross-time coupling issues that render BP inapplicable. As demonstrated in the manuscript, the forward-forward method enables stable gradient computation and effective training of FRNNs, which would otherwise be intractable with BP. We have revised the manuscript to emphasize this critical distinction, clarifying that the forward-forward method is a necessary approach for FRNNs due to the fundamental incompatibility of BP with the network’s structure. We hope this explanation addresses your concern.

Recent advances in fractional-order neural architectures have introduced optimization strategies to improve training efficiency and accuracy. Fractional-order convolutional neural networks (FOCNNs) employ the Caputo fractional-order gradient method (CFOGM) for faster convergence and better avoidance of local minima [9]. To enhance initialization and parameter tuning, population extremal optimization (PEO) has been combined with FOCNN, forming the PEO-FOCNN framework [24]. Furthermore, fractional order derivatives (FOD) have been introduced as tunable parameters in activation functions, enabling flexible adaptation and improved performance [20]. Experiments on datasets such as MNIST show that fractional activation functions—especially fractional Sigmoid—can outperform traditional methods in accuracy and efficiency, underscoring the potential of fractional-order approaches

for architectures where backpropagation faces structural limitations. The proposed architecture is defined as:

$$\nabla^{\vec{\alpha}} \vec{o}(t) = \vec{f}(\vec{i}(t), \vec{o}(t-1)), \quad (2)$$

where $\vec{\alpha} = [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_\mu]^T$ is a vector of fractional orders, and the operator $\nabla^{\vec{\alpha}}$ is applied component-wise:

$$\nabla^{\vec{\alpha}} \vec{o}(t) = [\nabla^{\alpha_1} o_1(t), \dots, \nabla^{\alpha_\mu} o_\mu(t)]^T. \quad (3)$$

Each component $\nabla^{\alpha_i} o_i(t)$ for $\alpha_i \in [0, 1]$ is defined as:

$$\nabla^{\alpha_i} o_i(t) = \nabla \nabla^{-(1-\alpha_i)} o_i(t), \quad t \in \mathbb{N}_1, \quad (4)$$

where the backward difference operator is:

$$\nabla o_i(t) = o_i(t) - o_i(t-1), \quad (5)$$

and the fractional sum is given by:

$$\nabla^{-(1-\alpha_i)} o_i(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha_i)} \sum_{s=0}^t \frac{\Gamma(t-s+1-\alpha_i)}{\Gamma(t-s+1)} o_i(s). \quad (6)$$

Compared to existing methods, our approach offers:

- Adaptive memory representation through learnable fractional orders.
- A unified framework that reduces to classical RNNs or memoryless systems under special cases.
- Enhanced modeling capability for heterogeneous sequential data.

The main contributions of this work are:

1. A novel FRNN architecture based on incommensurate nabla fractional dynamics.
2. Theoretical analysis of its properties and relationships to classical RNNs.
3. Empirical validation on synthetic benchmarks and a real-world forecasting case study.

2. Incommensurate algebra and preliminaries

Incommensurate systems necessitate a specialized algebraic framework that diverges from classical algebra due to the requirement of element-wise operations. In this section, we follow the notation conventions established in [4,25–27], which are consistent with the dotted indexing style commonly used in MATLAB.

Let \vec{o} and \vec{q} be vectors of dimension μ . The arithmetic operations in the incommensurate context are defined component-wise as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{o} \pm \vec{q} &= [o_1 \pm q_1, \dots, o_\mu \pm q_\mu]^T, \\ \vec{o} \circ \vec{q} &= [o_1 q_1, \dots, o_\mu q_\mu]^T, \\ \vec{o}^{\vec{q}} &= [o_1^{q_1}, \dots, o_\mu^{q_\mu}]^T, \\ \frac{\vec{o}}{\vec{q}} &= \left[\frac{o_1}{q_1}, \dots, \frac{o_\mu}{q_\mu} \right]^T, \\ \vec{o} \pm c &= [o_1 \pm c, \dots, o_\mu \pm c]^T, \\ c \vec{o} &= [c o_1, \dots, c o_\mu]^T, \\ c^{\vec{o}} &= [c^{o_1}, \dots, c^{o_\mu}]^T, \\ \vec{o}^c &= [o_1^c, \dots, o_\mu^c]^T, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where c is a scalar constant.

For a scalar-valued function f , its application to a vector is defined element-wise:

$$f(\vec{o}) = [f(o_1), \dots, f(o_\mu)]^T.$$

If $\vec{f} = [f_1, \dots, f_\mu]^T$ is a vector of functions, then:

$$\vec{f}(\vec{o}) = [f_1(o_1), \dots, f_\mu(o_\mu)]^T = (\text{Diag}(\vec{f}))\vec{o}.$$

To work with the fractional nabla difference operator, we decompose it into two components: the tail operator and the peak (identity) operator. Let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $o : \mathbb{N}_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^\alpha o(t) &= \nabla^{-(1-\alpha)} o(t) - \nabla^{-(1-\alpha)} o(t-1) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \sum_{s=0}^t \frac{\Gamma(t-s+1-\alpha)}{\Gamma(t-s+1)} o(s) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \frac{\Gamma(t-s-\alpha)}{\Gamma(t-s)} o(s) \\ &= o(t) - \frac{\alpha}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \frac{\Gamma(t-s-\alpha)}{\Gamma(t-s)} o(s), \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

for $t \in \mathbb{N}_1$. We define the tail operator T^α as:

$$T^\alpha o(t) := - \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \gamma_s(t, \alpha) o(s), \tag{9}$$

where

$$\gamma_s(t, \alpha) := \frac{\alpha \Gamma(t-s-\alpha)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha) \Gamma(t-s)}, \quad s = 0, \dots, t-1. \tag{10}$$

Specifically, for $s = t-1$:

$$\gamma_{t-1}(t, \alpha) = \alpha,$$

and for $s = 0$:

$$\gamma_0(t, \alpha) = \alpha \frac{(t-1-\alpha)}{(t-1)} \dots \frac{(1-\alpha)}{1}.$$

Theorem 1. Let $\alpha > 0$. Then,

$$\frac{\partial \gamma_s(t, \alpha)}{\partial \alpha} = \begin{cases} 1, & s = t-1, \\ \frac{1}{(t-s-1)!} \sum_{r=0}^{t-s-1} \prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq r}}^{t-s-1} (i-\alpha), & 0 \leq s < t-1. \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

Proof. For $s = t-1$, we have:

$$\frac{\Gamma(t-s-\alpha)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} = 1.$$

For $s < t-1$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Gamma(t-s-\alpha)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} &= \frac{(t-s-1-\alpha)\Gamma(t-s-1-\alpha)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \\ &= (t-s-1-\alpha) \dots (1-\alpha). \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Thus, the expression becomes:

$$-\gamma_s(t, \alpha) = \frac{(t-s-1-\alpha) \dots (-\alpha)}{(t-s-1) \dots (1)}.$$

Differentiating with respect to α yields:

$$\frac{d}{d\alpha} (-\gamma_s(t, \alpha)) = \frac{-1}{(t-s-1)!} \sum_{r=0}^{t-s-1} \prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq r}}^{t-s-1} (i-\alpha). \tag{13}$$

Eq. (11) follows directly from (13). \square

Hence, Eq. (8) can be expressed more compactly as:

$$\nabla^\alpha o(t) = o(t) + T^\alpha o(t) = o(t) - \alpha \nabla^{-(1-\alpha)} o(t-1). \tag{14}$$

Extending this to the vector case, for $\vec{\alpha} = [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_\mu]^T$, the incommensurate tail operator is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} T^{\vec{\alpha}} \vec{o}(t) &= [T^{\alpha_1} o_1(t), \dots, T^{\alpha_\mu} o_\mu(t)]^T \\ &= - \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \gamma_s(t, \vec{\alpha}) \circ \vec{o}(s), \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

and the incommensurate nabla operator becomes:

$$\nabla^{\vec{\alpha}} \vec{o}(t) = T^{\vec{\alpha}} \vec{o}(t) + \vec{o}(t) = [\nabla^{\alpha_1} o_1(t), \dots, \nabla^{\alpha_\mu} o_\mu(t)]^T. \tag{16}$$

3. Dense incommensurate fractional RNN

In this section, we present the forward computation process used to evaluate the output of the network, followed by the backward computation (backpropagation) for learning the model parameters.

3.1. Forward propagation

Let $W^{[i]} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mu_i \times \mu_{i-1}}$ be the weight matrix between the $(i-1)$ -th and i -th layers (with $\mu_0 = \nu$, where ν is the dimension of the input layer), $P^{[1]} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mu_1 \times \mu_n}$ (with $\mu_n = \mu$, where μ is the dimension of the expected output) be the recurrent weight matrix at the first layer, and $\vec{b}^{[i]} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mu_i}$ the bias vector. The activation functions $g^{[i]} : \mathbb{R}^{\mu_i} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\mu_i}$ are assumed to be differentiable, for $i = 1, \dots, n$.

The forward propagation is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{z}^{[1]}(t) &= W^{[1]} \vec{q}^{[0]}(t) + P^{[1]} \vec{o}(t-1) + \vec{b}^{[1]}, \\ \vec{q}^{[1]}(t) &= g^{[1]}(\vec{z}^{[1]}(t)), \\ \vec{z}^{[k]}(t) &= W^{[k]} \vec{q}^{[k-1]}(t) + \vec{b}^{[k]}, \quad k = 2, \dots, n, \\ \vec{q}^{[k]}(t) &= g^{[k]}(\vec{z}^{[k]}(t)), \quad k = 2, \dots, n, \\ \nabla^{\vec{\alpha}} \vec{o}(t) &= \vec{q}^{[n]}(t), \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

where $\vec{q}^{[0]}(t) = \vec{i}(t)$ is the input at time t .

Using the decomposition from Eq. (14), the output $\vec{o}(t)$ can be explicitly written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{o}(t) &= \vec{q}^{[n]}(t) + \vec{\alpha} \circ \nabla^{-(1-\vec{\alpha})} \vec{o}(t-1) \\ &= \vec{q}^{[n]}(t) + \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \gamma_s(t, \vec{\alpha}) \circ \vec{o}(s), \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

where the fractional memory term $\nabla^{-(1-\vec{\alpha})} \vec{o}(t-1)$ captures the influence of the past outputs.

Remark 1. In Eq. (17), the fractional orders $\alpha_i \in (0, 1]$ define the order of memory associated with each output component. Eq. (18) allows the relaxation of this condition. Although it is possible to constrain α_i during training, doing so has no significant advantage and is not enforced.

4. Gradient computation for the FRNN

A key distinction between artificial neural networks (ANNs)—often analogized to “artificial brains”—and the Fractional Recurrent Neural Network (FRNN) lies in layer-specific structural diversity: ANNs may differ in activation functions, connection topologies, or layer dimensions, but the FRNN introduces additional complexity due to its two core dimensions: “depth” (n , i.e., number of layers) and “terminal time step” (T). This complexity fundamentally changes how gradients are computed, compared to classical ANNs.

In classical ANNs, back-propagation is a well-established method for calculating gradients by propagating error signals backward through the

network’s depth. However, this method fails for the FRNN, necessitating a new approach: “forward-forward-gradient computation”, which we propose herein to handle the FRNN’s unique temporal and layer-wise dependencies.

To illustrate why back-propagation is invalid for the FRNN, consider the state Eq. (17) (defining FRNN states) at different time steps: 1. At $t = 1$: The state vector $\bar{z}^{[k]}(1)$ (for layer k) is linear with respect to its corresponding weight matrix $W^{[k]}$ and independent of weights in subsequent layers ($W^{[k+1]}, \dots, W^{[n]}$). This aligns with classical ANN behavior, where layer k depends only on prior layers. 2. At $t = 2$ (and all $t > 1$): The output $\bar{o}(1)$ (from $t = 1$) couples parameters across all layers. As a result:

- $\bar{z}^{[k]}(2)$ is no longer linear with respect to $W^{[k]}$;
- $\bar{z}^{[k]}(2)$ depends on weights from both past layers (as in classical ANNs) and subsequent layers (a FRNN-specific dependency);
- The fractional orders α_i (for $i = 1, \dots, \nu$) exert a distributed influence across all temporal states, further complicating parameter dependencies.

This cross-layer and cross-time coupling (evident for $t > 1$) breaks the sequential backward-propagation logic. Thus, we propose “forward-forward propagation” to compute gradients for the FRNN, leveraging its temporal recurrence to resolve these dependencies.

In general, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{z}^{[1]}(t) &= W^{[1]}\bar{q}^{[0]}(t) + P^{[1]}\bar{o}(t-1) + \bar{b}^{[1]}, \\ \bar{q}^{[1]}(t) &= g^{[1]}(\bar{z}^{[1]}(t)), \\ \bar{z}^{[k]}(t) &= W^{[k]}\bar{q}^{[k-1]}(t) + \bar{b}^{[k]}, \quad k = 2, \dots, n, \\ \bar{q}^{[k]}(t) &= g^{[k]}(\bar{z}^{[k]}(t)), \quad k = 2, \dots, n, \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

$$\bar{o}(t) = \bar{q}^{[n]}(t) + \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \gamma_s(t, \bar{\alpha}) \circ \bar{o}(s),$$

Let $t = 1$,

$$\frac{\partial z_i^{[k]}(1)}{\partial \theta} = \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_0} \frac{\partial w_{ij}^{[k]}}{\partial \theta} q_j^{[0]}(1) + \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_n} \frac{\partial p_{ij}^{[1]}}{\partial \theta} o_j(0) + \frac{\partial b_i^{[1]}}{\partial \theta} \tag{20}$$

and

$$\frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(1)}{\partial \theta} = (g^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(1)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(1)}{\partial \theta}, \quad i = 1, \dots, \mu_1, \tag{21}$$

for $k = 2, \dots, n$

$$\frac{\partial z_i^{[k]}(1)}{\partial \theta} = \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_{k-1}} \left(w_{ij}^{[k]} \frac{\partial q_j^{[k-1]}(1)}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial w_{ij}^{[k]}}{\partial \theta} q_j^{[k-1]}(1) \right) + \frac{\partial b_i^{[k]}}{\partial \theta} \tag{22}$$

$$\frac{\partial q_i^{[k]}(1)}{\partial \theta} = (g^{[k]})'(z_i^{[k]}(1)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[k]}(1)}{\partial \theta}, \quad i = 1, \dots, \mu_k, \tag{23}$$

and

$$\frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial \theta} = \frac{\partial q_i^{[n]}(1)}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \gamma_0(1, \alpha_i)}{\partial \theta} o_i(0), \quad i = 1, \dots, \mu_n, \tag{24}$$

For $t = 2, \dots, T$, $k = 1, \dots, n$, we use the following recursive formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial z_i^{[k]}(t)}{\partial \theta} &= \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_{k-1}} \left(w_{ij}^{[k]} \frac{\partial q_j^{[k-1]}(t)}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial w_{ij}^{[k]}}{\partial \theta} q_j^{[k-1]}(t) \right) \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_n} \left(p_{ij}^{[k]} \frac{\partial o_j(t-1)}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial p_{ij}^{[k]}}{\partial \theta} o_j(t-1) \right) + \frac{\partial b_i^{[k]}}{\partial \theta}, \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

$$\frac{\partial q_i^{[k]}(t)}{\partial \theta} = (g^{[k]})'(z_i^{[k]}(t)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[k]}(t)}{\partial \theta},$$

Algorithm 1 FRNN gradient computation.

Require: Network parameters, initial input $\bar{q}^{[0]}(t)$, initial output guess $\bar{o}(0)$, terminal timestep T , layer sizes μ_i for $i = 1, \dots, n$

Ensure: Gradients of FRNN outputs with respect to parameters θ

- 1: **Initial Timestep** ($t = 1$)
 - 2: Compute $\bar{z}^{[1]}(1)$ using Eq. (19)
 - 3: **for** $i = 1$ **to** μ_1 **do**
 - 4: Compute $\frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(1)}{\partial \theta}$ for $\theta \in \{W^{[1]}, P^{[1]}, \bar{b}^{[1]}\}$ using Eq. (20)
 - 5: **for** $\theta \in \{W^{[k]}, \bar{b}^{[k]}, \bar{\alpha} \mid k \neq 1\}$ **do**
 - 6: Set $\frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(1)}{\partial \theta} = \vec{0}_{\dim(\theta)}$
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: Compute $\bar{q}^{[1]}(1)$ using Eq. (19)
 - 9: Compute $\frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(1)}{\partial \theta}$ using Eq. (21)
 - 10: **for** $j = 2$ **to** n **do**
 - 11: Compute $\bar{z}^{[j]}(1)$ and $\bar{q}^{[j]}(1)$ using Eq. (19)
 - 12: Compute $\frac{\partial z_i^{[j]}(1)}{\partial \theta}$ and $\frac{\partial q_i^{[j]}(1)}{\partial \theta}$ using Eqs. (22) and (23)
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: Compute $\bar{o}(1)$ using Eq. (19)
 - 15: Compute $\frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial \theta}$ using Eq. (24)
 - 16: **end for**
 - 17: **Subsequent Timesteps** ($t = 2, \dots, T$)
 - 18: **for** $t = 2$ **to** T **do**
 - 19: **for** $j = 1$ **to** n **do**
 - 20: Compute $\bar{z}^{[j]}(t)$ and $\bar{q}^{[j]}(t)$ using Eq. (19)
 - 21: Compute $\frac{\partial z_i^{[j]}(t)}{\partial \theta}$ and $\frac{\partial q_i^{[j]}(t)}{\partial \theta}$ using Eq. (25)
 - 22: **end for**
 - 23: Compute $\bar{o}(t)$ using Eq. (19)
 - 24: Compute $\frac{\partial o_i(t)}{\partial \theta}$ using Eq. (26)
 - 25: **end for**
-

and

$$\frac{\partial o_i(t)}{\partial \theta} = \frac{\partial q_i^{[n]}(t)}{\partial \theta} + \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \left(\frac{\partial \gamma_s(t, \alpha_i)}{\partial \theta} o_i(s) + \gamma_s(t, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(s)}{\partial \theta} \right) \tag{26}$$

The forward-forward formula is described in Algorithm 1.

5. Gradient of the energy function

In neural network optimization, a central objective is to compute the gradient of the energy (or cost) function with respect to the model parameters. The energy function is defined as:

$$E_I = \sum_{r \in I} \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_n} \left(o_j(T) - y_j^{[r]} \right)^2 = \sum_{r \in I} C_T(r), \tag{27}$$

where

$$C_T(r) = \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_n} \left(o_j(T) - y_j^{[r]} \right)^2. \tag{28}$$

Here, $\bar{y}^{[r]} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mu_n}$ denotes the target output vector corresponding to the input $\bar{y}^{[r]} \in \mathbb{R}^{\nu}$, and r indexes the training samples. The set $I \subset \mathbb{N}$ is a finite index set representing the training dataset.

The total gradient of the energy function with respect to a parameter θ is given by:

$$\frac{dE_I}{d\theta} = \sum_{r \in I} \frac{dC_T(r)}{d\theta}. \tag{29}$$

Each term in the sum is computed as:

$$\frac{\partial C_T(r)}{\partial \theta} = 2 \left(\bar{o}(T) - \bar{y}^{[r]} \right) \circ \frac{\partial \bar{o}(T)}{\partial \theta}, \tag{30}$$

where \circ denotes the Hadamard (element-wise) product.

6. Learning algorithm

To train the FRNN, we employ mini-batch Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) combined with the Adaptive Moment Estimation (ADAM) optimizer [18]. Let θ denote the set of trainable parameters, including: Layer weights $W_{ij}^{[k]}$, - Recurrent weights $P_{ij}^{[k]}$, - Biases $b_j^{[k]}$, - Fractional orders α_j .

Let N_b be the number of mini-batches, and let I_j for $j = 1, \dots, N_b$ be a partition of the training index set I , such that:

$$I = \text{Randperm}\{1, \dots, N_T\} = \bigcup_{j=1}^{N_b} I_j,$$

where N_T is the total number of training samples and Randperm denotes a random permutation of indices to ensure stochasticity.

For each mini-batch I_j , the ADAM update rule is:

$$\begin{aligned} g &\leftarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \sum_{r \in I_j} C_T(r), \\ m &\leftarrow \frac{\beta_1 m + (1 - \beta_1)g}{1 - \beta_1^n}, \\ \zeta &\leftarrow \frac{\beta_2 \zeta + (1 - \beta_2)g^2}{1 - \beta_2^n}, \\ \theta &\leftarrow \theta - \eta \frac{m}{\sqrt{\zeta} + \epsilon}, \\ n &\leftarrow n + 1, \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where: - m is the first moment estimate (initialized to zero), - ζ is the second moment estimate (also initialized to zero), - $\beta_1 = 0.9$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$ are exponential decay rates, - $\epsilon = 10^{-8}$ is a small constant for numerical stability, - η is the learning rate, - n is the iteration counter.

Training proceeds until $n = N_{\text{ADAM}}$, where $N_{\text{ADAM}} \in \mathbb{N}$ is a user-defined maximum number of ADAM iterations.

While the ADAM optimization method has demonstrated significant acceleration in experimental settings, its theoretical analysis remains incomplete, particularly across diverse problem scenarios and in relation to mini-batch size selection. Reddi et al. [22] revealed that the ADAM method may exhibit divergence in certain cases, attributed to the decreasing sequence $\eta_t^{-1} - \eta_{t-1}^{-1}$ of the learning rate. To address this issue, they proposed generalized variants of ADAM that ensure convergence guarantees.

Chen et al. [10] investigated the convergence-related parameters of the base learning rate and combinations of historical second-order moments, establishing conditions for the global convergence of the standard ADAM method in large-scale non-convex stochastic optimization problems.

Notably, several studies have reported the convergence of ADAM when employing full-batch gradients or large batch sizes (e.g., [28]).

Currently, numerous preprints on the convergence of ADAM across diverse scenarios have been published on arXiv, awaiting peer review. Given this context, we argue that further research is required to analyze the ADAM method with mini-batch learning for our proposed FRNN.

7. Analysis (Boundedness of the gradient)

This section focuses on analyzing the boundedness of the gradient variance for FRNNs. Particularly, we establish the boundedness of the gradient variance for single-layer FRNNs with iteration steps $T = 1$ and $T = 2$. The boundedness of gradient variance is crucial for ensuring the stability and convergence of the neural network during the training process.

We have the following assumptions in our analysis:

Assump. (1) The activation functions $g^{[k]}$ and their derivatives $(g^{[k]})'$ are bounded by a constant G . This assumption holds for most common activation functions, such as sigmoid, sin, and tanh.

Assump. (2) The activation functions are bounded by 1, which is satisfied by well-known activation functions like sigmoid, sin, and tanh.

Define

$$Y = \max_{i,s,\theta} |\partial_\theta \gamma_0(s, \alpha_i)|$$

and

$$\max_{i,j} |p_{ij}| = M_{p,r}.$$

Also, in this section, we use the fact that

$$\gamma_s(t, \alpha_i) < 1,$$

for all $s = 0, 1, \dots, t-1$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, \mu_n$.

Definition 1. The variance of the gradient over the learning parameter θ is defined as:

$$V(\partial_\theta E_I) = \frac{1}{|I|} \sum_{r \in I} (\partial_\theta C_T(r) - \overline{\partial_\theta C_T(r)})^2$$

where $\partial_\theta = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta}$, $|I|$ denotes the number of training samples, and $\overline{\partial_\theta C_T(r)}$ is the mean of $\partial_\theta C_T(r)$ over the training set I .

Theorem 2. For a single-layer FRNN $T = 1$ and $T = 2$, with learning parameters $\theta \in \{w_{ij}^{[1]}, p_{ij}^{[1]}, b_j^{[1]}, \alpha_j\}$, the variance of the gradient with respect to the learning parameters is a bounded operator.

Proof. Boundedness Analysis for $T = 1$:

From (30), we have:

$$\partial_\theta C_T(r) = 2 (\bar{o}(T) - \bar{y}^{[r]}) \circ \partial_\theta \bar{o}(T) \quad (32)$$

By the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality:

$$|\partial_\theta C_T(r)| \leq 2 \|\bar{o}(T) - \bar{y}^{[r]}\| \cdot \|\partial_\theta \bar{o}(T)\| \quad (33)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ represents the Euclidean norm. When $t = 1$, from (24):

$$\|\partial_\theta \bar{o}(1)\| \leq \|\partial_\theta \bar{q}^{[1]}(1)\| + |\partial_\theta \gamma_0(1, \alpha_i)| \|o_i(0)\| \quad (34)$$

From (21):

$$\|\partial_\theta \bar{q}^{[1]}(1)\| \leq \max_i |(g^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(1))| \cdot \|\partial_\theta \bar{z}^{[1]}(1)\| \leq G \|\partial_\theta \bar{z}^{[1]}(1)\| \quad (35)$$

Moreover,

$$\|\partial_\theta \bar{z}^{[1]}(1)\| \leq \max_i \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_0} |\partial_\theta w_{ij}^{[1]}| \cdot \|\bar{q}^{[0]}(1)\| + \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_1} |\partial_\theta p_{ij}^{[1]}| \cdot \|\bar{o}(0)\| + |\partial_\theta b_i^{[1]}| \quad (36)$$

Since $\sum_{j=1}^{\mu_1} |\partial_\theta p_{ij}^{[1]}| = \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_1} |\delta_{\theta, p_{ij}}| \leq 1$, $\sum_{j=1}^{\mu_0} |\partial_\theta w_{ij}^{[1]}| \leq 1$ and $\sum_{j=1}^{\mu_1} |\partial_\theta b_i^{[1]}| \leq 1$, we can obtain:

$$\|\partial_\theta \bar{z}^{[1]}(1)\| \leq \|\bar{q}^{[0]}(1)\| + \|\bar{o}(0)\| \quad (37)$$

Substituting this into (35), we get:

$$\|\partial_\theta \bar{q}^{[1]}(1)\| \leq G (\|\bar{q}^{[0]}(1)\| + \|\bar{o}(0)\|) \quad (38)$$

Further substituting into (34):

$$\|\partial_\theta \bar{o}(1)\| \leq G (\|\bar{q}^{[0]}(1)\| + \|\bar{o}(0)\|) + Y \|o_i(0)\| \leq (G + Y) (\|\bar{q}^{[0]}(1)\| + \|\bar{o}(0)\|) \quad (39)$$

Since the activation functions are bounded by 1, $\|\bar{\alpha}(1) - \bar{y}^{[r]}\| \leq 1$. Thus, from (33):

$$|\partial_\theta C_1(r)| \leq 2\|\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(1)\| \leq 2(G + \Upsilon) (\|\bar{q}^{[0]}(1)\| + \|\bar{\alpha}(0)\|) \quad (40)$$

This shows that $\partial_\theta C_1(r)$ is bounded, so the variance $V(\partial_\theta E_T)$ is bounded for $T = 1$.

Boundedness Analysis for $T = 2$:

When $t = 2$, from (24):

$$\begin{aligned} \|\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(2)\| &\leq \|\partial_\theta \bar{q}^{[1]}(2)\| + \max |\partial_\theta \gamma_0(2, \alpha_i)| \cdot \|\bar{\alpha}(0)\| \\ &\quad + \max |\partial_\theta \gamma_1(2, \alpha_i)| \cdot \|\bar{\alpha}(1)\| + \max |\gamma_1(2, \alpha_i)| \cdot \|\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(1)\| \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Since $\gamma_s(t, \alpha_i) < 1$ and $\Upsilon = \max_{i,s,\theta} |\partial_\theta \gamma_0(s, \alpha_i)|$, we have:

$$\|\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(2)\| \leq \|\partial_\theta \bar{q}^{[1]}(2)\| + \Upsilon \|\bar{\alpha}(0)\| + \Upsilon \|\bar{\alpha}(1)\| + \|\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(1)\| \quad (42)$$

Considering that the activation functions are bounded by 1, $\|\bar{\alpha}(1)\| \leq 1$, and using (39):

$$\|\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(2)\| \leq \|\partial_\theta \bar{q}^{[1]}(2)\| + \Upsilon \|\bar{\alpha}(0)\| + \Upsilon + (G + \Upsilon) (\|\bar{q}^{[0]}(1)\| + \|\bar{\alpha}(0)\|) \quad (43)$$

Next, analyze $\|\partial_\theta \bar{q}^{[1]}(2)\|$ from (25):

$$\begin{aligned} |\partial_\theta q_i^{[1]}(2)| &\leq G |z_i^{[1]}(2)| \\ &\leq G \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_1} \left(|w_{ij}^{[1]}| \cdot |\partial_\theta q_j^{[0]}(2)| \right) + G |q_j^{[0]}(2)| \\ &\quad + G \sum_{j=1}^{\mu_1} \left(|p_{ij}^{[1]}| \cdot |\partial_\theta o_j(1)| \right) + G |o_j(1)| + G \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

Since $q_j^{[0]}(2)$ is an input parameter, $|\partial_\theta q_j^{[0]}(2)| = 0$. Recalling $\max_{i,j} |p_{ij}| = M_{P,r}$ and considering $\|\bar{\alpha}(1)\| \leq 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\partial_\theta \bar{q}^{[1]}(2)\| &\leq G \|\bar{q}^{[0]}(2)\| + G \mu_1 M_{P,r} \cdot \|\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(1)\| + G \|\bar{\alpha}(1)\| + G \\ &\leq G \|\bar{q}^{[0]}(2)\| + G \mu_1 M_{P,r} (G + \Upsilon) (\|\bar{q}^{[0]}(1)\| + \|\bar{\alpha}(0)\|) + 2G \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

Substituting this back into the expression of $\|\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(2)\|$, we can conclude that $\|\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(2)\|$ is bounded. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} |\partial_\theta C_2(r)| &\leq 2\|\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(2)\| \\ &\leq 2G \|\bar{q}^{[0]}(2)\| + 2G \mu_1 M_{P,r} (G + \Upsilon) (\|\bar{q}^{[0]}(1)\| + \|\bar{\alpha}(0)\|) \\ &\quad + 4G + 2\Upsilon \|\bar{\alpha}(0)\| + 2\Upsilon + 2(G + \Upsilon) (\|\bar{q}^{[0]}(1)\| + \|\bar{\alpha}(0)\|) \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

is bounded, and the variance $V(\partial_\theta E_T)$ is bounded for $T = 2$. \square

Remark 2. For $T > 2$, we can use inductive reasoning. Assume that for $T = k$ ($k \geq 2$), the variance of the gradient is bounded. When $T = k + 1$, applying the same analysis method as for $T = 1$ and $T = 2$, and considering the boundedness of activation functions, their derivatives, and network parameters, we can prove that $\partial_\theta \bar{\alpha}(k + 1)$ is bounded. Further, combined with the boundedness of $\|\bar{\alpha}(k + 1) - \bar{y}^{[r]}\|$, we obtain that $|\partial_\theta C_{k+1}(r)|$ is bounded, so the variance $V(\partial_\theta E_T)$ is bounded. Therefore, the variance of the gradient is a bounded operator for any T .

8. Illustrative examples

A key application of the proposed Fractional Recurrent Neural Network (FRNN) is time series forecasting. In this section, we demonstrate how the FRNN can be trained using historical data to predict future values.

Example 1. Let us consider the time series defined by $x(t) = \sin(0.05t)$, which may represent daily temperature measurements over a year (e.g., $t = 1, \dots, 365$). In our setup, we use ν past observations to predict the next m future values. Specifically, the input and target vectors are constructed as:

$$\bar{x}(t) = [x(t), \dots, x(t - 1 + \nu)]^T, \quad \bar{y}(t) = [x(t + 1), \dots, x(t + m)]^T.$$

For comparison purposes, we set $m = 5$ and $\nu = 100$, meaning the model uses the last 100 days to forecast the next 5 days.

We consider a single-layer FRNN with the following parameter dimensions:

$$W^{[1]} \in \mathbb{R}^{5 \times 100}, \quad P^{[1]} \in \mathbb{R}^{5 \times 5}, \quad \bar{b}^{[1]} \in \mathbb{R}^5, \quad \bar{\alpha} \in \mathbb{R}^5, \quad \mu_1 = \mu = 5.$$

To clarify Algorithm 1, we detail the forward computation for this FRNN. At time step t , the network evolves as:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{z}^{[1]}(t) &= W^{[1]} \bar{q}^{[0]}(t) + P^{[1]} \bar{\alpha}(t - 1) + \bar{b}^{[1]}, \\ \bar{q}^{[1]}(t) &= g^{[1]}(\bar{z}^{[1]}(t)), \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}(t) = \bar{q}^{[1]}(t) + \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \gamma_s(t, \bar{\alpha}) \circ \bar{\alpha}(s).$$

Let $t = 1$. For each output component $i = 1, \dots, 5$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} z_i^{[1]}(1) &= \sum_{j=1}^{100} W_{ij}^{[1]} q_j^{[0]}(1) + \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} o_j(0) + b_i^{[1]}, \\ q_i^{[1]}(1) &= g_i^{[1]}(z_i^{[1]}(1)), \\ o_i(1) &= q_i^{[1]}(1) + \gamma_0(1, \alpha_i) o_i(0). \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

1. Derivative with respect to $\bar{\alpha}$:

$$\frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial \bar{\alpha}} = \gamma_0'(1, \alpha_i) o_i(0) \epsilon_i = o_i(0) \epsilon_i, \quad (49)$$

where ϵ_i is the i -th standard basis vector.

2. Derivative with respect to $W^{[1]}$:

$$\frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial W^{[1]}} = (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(1)) \bar{q}^{[0]}(1)^T \circ \epsilon_i, \quad (50)$$

3. Derivative with respect to $P^{[1]}$:

$$\frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial P^{[1]}} = (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(1)) \bar{\alpha}(0)^T \circ \epsilon_i, \quad (51)$$

4. Derivative with respect to $\bar{b}^{[1]}$:

$$\frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial \bar{b}^{[1]}} = (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(1)) \epsilon_i. \quad (52)$$

Given a target vector $\bar{y}^{[r]} \in \mathbb{R}^5$ and time step $T = 1$, the gradient of the loss function $C_1(r)$ with respect to each parameter is:

1. Derivative with respect to $W^{[1]}$:

$$\frac{\partial C_1(r)}{\partial W^{[1]}} = 2(\bar{\alpha}(1) - \bar{y}^{[r]}) \circ (\bar{g}^{[1]})'(\bar{z}^{[1]}(1)) \circ \begin{pmatrix} \bar{q}^{[0]}(1)^T \\ \vdots \\ \bar{q}^{[0]}(1)^T \end{pmatrix}. \quad (53)$$

2. Derivative with respect to $P^{[1]}$:

$$\frac{\partial C_1(r)}{\partial P^{[1]}} = 2(\bar{\alpha}(1) - \bar{y}^{[r]}) \circ (\bar{g}^{[1]})'(\bar{z}^{[1]}(1)) \circ \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\alpha}(0)^T \\ \vdots \\ \bar{\alpha}(0)^T \end{pmatrix}. \quad (54)$$

3. Derivative with respect to $\vec{b}^{[1]}$:

$$\frac{\partial C_1(r)}{\partial \vec{b}^{[1]}} = 2(\vec{\alpha}(1) - \vec{y}^{[r]}) \circ (\vec{g}^{[1]})'(\vec{z}^{[1]}(1)). \quad (55)$$

4. Derivative with respect to $\vec{\alpha}$:

$$\frac{\partial C_1(r)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} = 2(\vec{\alpha}(1) - \vec{y}^{[r]}) \circ (\vec{g}^{[1]})'(\vec{z}^{[1]}(1)) \circ \vec{\alpha}(0). \quad (56)$$

At time step $T = 2$, the forward computation becomes:

$$z_i^{[1]}(2) = \sum_{j=1}^{100} W_{ij}^{[1]} q_j^{[0]}(2) + \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} o_j(1) + b_i^{[1]}, \quad (57)$$

$$q_i^{[1]}(2) = g_i^{[1]}(z_i^{[1]}(2)),$$

$$o_i(2) = q_i^{[1]}(2) + \gamma_0(2, \alpha_i) o_i(0) + \gamma_1(2, \alpha_i) o_i(1),$$

with memory coefficients:

$$\gamma_0(2, \alpha_i) = \alpha_i(1 - \alpha_i), \quad \gamma_1(2, \alpha_i) = \alpha_i.$$

Compared to $T = 1$, the gradient computation at $T = 2$ involves recursive dependencies on previous outputs and their gradients, resulting in more intricate expressions.

1. Derivative with respect to $\vec{\alpha}$ ($T = 2$)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial o_i(2)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} &= \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} + \frac{\partial \gamma_0(2, \alpha_i)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} o_i(0) + \frac{\partial \gamma_1(2, \alpha_i)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} o_i(1) + \gamma_1(2, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} \\ &= \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} + \gamma_0'(2, \alpha_i) \epsilon_i o_i(0) + \gamma_1'(2, \alpha_i) \epsilon_i o_i(1) + \gamma_1(2, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} \\ &= \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} + (1 - 2\alpha_i) \epsilon_i o_i(0) + \epsilon_i o_i(1) + \alpha_i \frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}}, \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

where $\frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}}$ is derived via the chain rule:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(2)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} \\ &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(2)) \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} \frac{\partial o_j(1)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}}. \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

2. Derivative with respect to $W^{[1]}$ ($T = 2$)

$$\frac{\partial o_i(2)}{\partial W^{[1]}} = \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial W^{[1]}} + \gamma_1(2, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial W^{[1]}}, \quad (60)$$

where $\frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial W^{[1]}}$ includes both the direct terms and the recursive terms from $T = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial W^{[1]}} &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(2)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial W^{[1]}} \\ &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(2)) \left(\vec{q}^{[0]}(2)^T \circ \epsilon_i + \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} \frac{\partial o_j(1)}{\partial W^{[1]}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

3. Derivative with respect to $P^{[1]}$ ($T = 2$)

$$\frac{\partial o_i(2)}{\partial P^{[1]}} = \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial P^{[1]}} + \gamma_1(2, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial P^{[1]}}, \quad (62)$$

where $\frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial P^{[1]}}$ is computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial P^{[1]}} &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(2)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial P^{[1]}} \\ &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(2)) \left(\vec{\alpha}(1)^T \circ \epsilon_i + \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} \frac{\partial o_j(1)}{\partial P^{[1]}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

4. Derivative with respect to $\vec{b}^{[1]}$ ($T = 2$)

$$\frac{\partial o_i(2)}{\partial \vec{b}^{[1]}} = \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial \vec{b}^{[1]}} + \gamma_1(2, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(1)}{\partial \vec{b}^{[1]}}, \quad (64)$$

where $\frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial \vec{b}^{[1]}}$ follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial \vec{b}^{[1]}} &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(2)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(2)}{\partial \vec{b}^{[1]}} \\ &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(2)) \left(\epsilon_i + \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} \frac{\partial o_j(1)}{\partial \vec{b}^{[1]}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

Finally for $\theta \in \{W^{[1]}, P^{[1]}, b^{[1]}, \alpha\}$, the partial derivative of the loss $C_2(r)$ (at $T = 2$) with respect to θ is:

$$\frac{\partial C_2(r)}{\partial \theta} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^{u_n} (o_j(2) - y_j^{[r]}) \frac{\partial o_j(2)}{\partial \theta} \quad (66)$$

In general for any time step $t = 1, \dots, T$, $T \geq 2$, the forward propagation of the FRNN is:

$$\begin{aligned} z_i^{[1]}(t) &= \sum_{j=1}^{100} W_{ij}^{[1]} q_j^{[0]}(t) + \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} o_j(t-1) + b_i^{[1]}, \\ q_i^{[1]}(t) &= g_i^{[1]}(z_i^{[1]}(t)), \\ o_i(t) &= q_i^{[1]}(t) + \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \gamma_s(t, \alpha_i) o_i(s). \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

The derivative with respect to α is computed by:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial o_i(t)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} &= \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} + \frac{\partial \gamma_0(t, \alpha_i)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} o_i(0) + \sum_{j=1}^{t-1} \left(\frac{\partial \gamma_j(t, \alpha_i)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} o_i(j) + \gamma_j(t, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(j)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} \right) \\ &= \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} + \gamma_0'(t, \alpha_i) \epsilon_i o_i(0) + \sum_{j=1}^{t-1} \left(\gamma_j'(t, \alpha_i) \epsilon_i o_i(j) + \gamma_j(t, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(j)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(t)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}} \\ &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(t)) \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} \frac{\partial o_j(t-1)}{\partial \vec{\alpha}}. \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

For the derivative with respect to $W^{[1]}$, we have

$$\frac{\partial o_i(t)}{\partial W^{[1]}} = \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial W^{[1]}} + \sum_{j=1}^{t-1} \gamma_j(t, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(j)}{\partial W^{[1]}}, \quad (70)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial W^{[1]}} &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(t)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial W^{[1]}} \\ &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(t)) \left(\vec{q}^{[0]}(t)^T \circ \epsilon_i + \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} \frac{\partial o_j(t-1)}{\partial W^{[1]}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

The derivative with respect to $P^{[1]}$ follows:

$$\frac{\partial o_i(t)}{\partial P^{[1]}} = \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial P^{[1]}} + \sum_{j=1}^{t-1} \gamma_j(t, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(j)}{\partial P^{[1]}}, \quad (72)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial P^{[1]}} &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(t)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial P^{[1]}} \\ &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(t)) \left(\bar{\alpha}(t-1)^T \circ \mathbf{c}_i + \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} \frac{\partial o_j(t-1)}{\partial P^{[1]}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

Finally, the derivative with respect to $\bar{b}^{[1]}$ is obtained by

$$\frac{\partial o_i(t)}{\partial \bar{b}^{[1]}} = \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial \bar{b}^{[1]}} + \sum_{j=1}^{t-1} \gamma_j(t, \alpha_i) \frac{\partial o_i(j)}{\partial \bar{b}^{[1]}}, \quad (74)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial q_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial \bar{b}^{[1]}} &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(t)) \frac{\partial z_i^{[1]}(t)}{\partial \bar{b}^{[1]}} \\ &= (g_i^{[1]})'(z_i^{[1]}(t)) \left(\mathbf{c}_i + \sum_{j=1}^5 P_{ij}^{[1]} \frac{\partial o_j(t-1)}{\partial \bar{b}^{[1]}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

For target vector $\mathbf{y}^{[r]}$ the partial derivative of loss function $C_T(r)$ with respect to any parameter $\theta \in \{W^{[1]}, P^{[1]}, b^{[1]}, \alpha\}$ is:

$$\frac{\partial C_T(r)}{\partial \theta} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^{u_n} (o_j(T) - y_j^{[r]}) \frac{\partial o_j(T)}{\partial \theta}. \quad (76)$$

To ensure fair experimental comparisons, we use fixed parameter initialization instead of random initialization. The initial values of all FRNN parameters are defined as follows:

$$W^{[1]} = \bar{1}_{5 \times 100} / (5 \times 100 \times 10), \quad P^{[1]} = \bar{1}_{5 \times 5} / (5 \times 5 \times 10), \quad b^{[1]} = \bar{1}_{5 \times 1} / (5 \times 1 \times 10),$$

and

$$\bar{\alpha} = [0.1, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3]^T$$

where $\bar{1}_{n \times m}$ is an $n \times m$ matrix with all elements equal to 1.

For model training, we adopt the Mini-Batch stochastic ADAM optimization method. The mini-batch size is fixed at 20, and the number of mini-batches $N_b = 10$. This means we use 200 samples for training (calculated as 20×10), which comes from a total dataset of 261 samples and accounts for 76.6 % of the full data.

We also define a specific learning rate for training:

$$\eta = \frac{0.02}{N_{\text{FRNN}}}$$

where $N_{\text{FRNN}} = 535$ is the total number of neurons in the FRNN. To ensure stable training of $\bar{\alpha}$ and enforce proper ordering of its values, we use a learning rate of 10η (10 times the base learning rate) when updating $\bar{\alpha}$.

The model's performance is evaluated using the Total Mean Squared Error (MSE), calculated by

$$E_{MSE}(T) = \frac{1}{261 \times 5} \sum_{r=1}^{261} \sum_{i=1}^5 (o_i(T) - y_i^{[r]})^2.$$

8.1. The effect of time step T

We employ the hyperbolic tangent function $g_i(t) = \tanh(t)$ (for $i = 1, \dots, 5$) as the activation function in the FRNN. Model training is performed using the ADAM optimizer, with $N_{\text{ADAM}} = 80$ iterations per mini-batch. Given a total of 10 mini-batches, this results in 800 training epochs.

Fig. 1 presents the Total Mean Squared Error $E_{MSE}(T)$ plotted against training epochs for various values of T . The figure demonstrates that

Fig. 1. Total mean squared error $E_{MSE}(T)$ versus training epochs for different time steps T , using the activation function $g_i(t) = \tanh(t)$.

Table 1

Total mean squared error E_{MSE} for different time steps T , using the FRNN with activation function $g_i(t) = \tanh(t)$.

T	1	2	3	4	5	6
E_{MSE}	0.0010	0.00080	0.00065	0.00053	0.00047	0.00038
T	7	8	9	10	11	12
E_{MSE}	0.00033	0.00023	0.00020	0.00032	0.00035	0.00043

Fig. 2. Evolution of fractional orders α_i during training for different time steps T , using the FRNN with activation function $g_i(t) = \tanh(t)$.

increasing the time step T initially leads to a reduction in $E_{MSE}(T)$, highlighting the benefits of the FRNN's recursive structure.

Table 1 reports the values of $E_{MSE}(T)$ for different time steps. As expected, the error decreases with increasing T up to a certain point. However, beyond $T = 10$, the error begins to rise again, indicating that deeper temporal recursion does not always yield better performance.

Fig. 2 illustrates the evolution of the fractional orders α_i during training for different values of T . While each α_i tends to decrease and stabilize over time, their relative ordering remains consistent throughout the training process.

8.2. The effect of activation function

We now examine the impact of using a different activation function. Specifically, we choose $g_i(t) = \sin(t)$ for $i = 1, \dots, 5$. Table 2 and Figs. 3 and 4 reveal similar trends to those observed with the hyperbolic tangent activation.

Table 2

Total mean squared error E_{MSE} for different time steps T , using the FRNN with activation function $g_i(t) = \sin(t)$.

T	1	2	3	4	5	6
E_{MSE}	0.00069	0.00057	0.00049	0.00039	0.00034	0.00032
T	7	8	9	10	11	12
E_{MSE}	0.00024	0.00022	0.00029	0.00038	0.00026	0.00047

Fig. 3. Total mean squared error $E_{MSE}(T)$ versus training epochs for different time steps T , using the activation function $g_i(t) = \sin(t)$.

Fig. 4. Evolution of fractional orders α_i during training for different time steps T , using the FRNN with activation function $g_i(t) = \sin(t)$.

- Table 2 shows that E_{MSE} decreases steadily until $T = 8$.
- Fig. 3 confirms that the error reduction is most significant during the early epochs for smaller values of T .
- Fig. 4 illustrates that the evolutionary pattern of the fractional orders α_i is preserved across different values of T .

8.3. The effect of initial $\vec{\alpha}$

In previous sections, we observed that the Mini-Batch ADAM optimizer tends to preserve the learning pattern—particularly the relative ordering of the fractional orders α_i —across different time steps T , especially when the initial vector $\vec{\alpha}$ is commensurate (i.e., elements have similar magnitudes). This suggests that the optimizer converges to locally optimal solutions while maintaining the initial structure of $\vec{\alpha}$.

To investigate this further, we randomly select six distinct initial vectors:

1. $\vec{\alpha}_1 = [0.4, 0.8, 0.5, 0.2, 0.4]^T$
2. $\vec{\alpha}_2 = [0.5, 0.02, 0.1, 0.6, 0.4]^T$
3. $\vec{\alpha}_3 = [0.9, 0.3, 0.5, 0.6, 0.1]^T$
4. $\vec{\alpha}_4 = [0.2, 0.3, 0.3, 0.1, 0.5]^T$
5. $\vec{\alpha}_5 = [0.3, 0.05, 0.6, 0.6, 0.2]^T$
6. $\vec{\alpha}_6 = [0.7, 0.3, 0.4, 0.3, 0.9]^T$

Fig. 5 shows the evolution of α_i for each initial vector. Three key observations emerge:

Commensurate order preservation: Elements with similar initial magnitudes tend to remain close during training. Examples include the 1st and 5th elements of $\vec{\alpha}_1$, the 2nd and 3rd of $\vec{\alpha}_4$, the 3rd and 4th of $\vec{\alpha}_5$, and the 2nd and 4th of $\vec{\alpha}_6$.

Strict relative order preservation: If $\alpha_i < \alpha_j$ initially, this inequality is preserved throughout training for all distinct indices $i, j \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$.

Direction of evolution: Most α_i values tend to decrease during training. However, values initially close to 1 do not exhibit this trend, as seen in Fig. 5(a), (c), and (f).

8.4. Linear scalability of FRNN

A key difference between FRNN and conventional fractional-order differential or difference systems lies in the use of a fixed range for T . Specifically, numerical methods for solving fractional-order systems often face challenges with the computational complexity of lag/memory terms (Eq. 18). This complexity causes computational time to grow non-linearly as T increases, where T is a parameter that affects numerical accuracy.

Fortunately, neural network applications do not require large values of T . As shown in the previous example (Table 2), optimal performance is achieved when $T = 8$. Consequently, the computational cost of the lag term in Eq. (18) becomes negligible. Thus, the total computational time for both training and inference of the FRNN scales approximately linearly with T .

This linear scalability is verified in Fig. 7: Fig. 7(a) plots elapsed training time against T , and Fig. 7(b) plots elapsed inference time against T . Both figures confirm the linear relationship between elapsed time and T . All experiments were conducted on a desktop with Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10510U CPU, 1.80 GHz (2.30 GHz) and MATLAB R2020b.

9. Experimental validations and comparisons on public real-world datasets

In all these examples, we use a simple fractional neural network with just one layer. We compare its results with other common fractional neural networks of the same type. Clearly, a dense fractional neural network would give better results; we'll work on that later. The reason is that its forward-backward process takes a lot of time, and calculating gradients is tricky. For now, we share these single-layer results as a preview, and we'll expand to dense networks in the future.

9.1. Electricity transformer temperature

The experimental data employed in this study is derived from the ETT (Electricity Transformer Temperature) dataset, originally presented in the work of Zhou et al. [29]. The dataset is publicly accessible on GitHub.¹

The ETT dataset comprises 2-year 24-hour-level time-series data (ETTM1 subset) collected from two distinct counties in China [29] (Fig. 6). Specifically, the ETTM1 subset includes a target variable (oil temperature) and six auxiliary power load features, which are tailored for long sequence time-series forecasting (LSTF) tasks.

¹ <https://github.com/zhouhaoyi/ETDataset>.

Fig. 5. Evolution of fractional orders α_i for different initial vectors $\vec{\alpha}$: (a) $\vec{\alpha}_1$, (b) $\vec{\alpha}_2$, (c) $\vec{\alpha}_3$, (d) $\vec{\alpha}_4$, (e) $\vec{\alpha}_5$, (f) $\vec{\alpha}_6$.

Fig. 6. ETT data: normalized oil temperature.

In this study, we focus on a multivariate time-series forecasting task: leveraging historical data of the target variable (oil temperature) to predict its future values. Specifically, the model takes the previous 30 days of oil temperature data for initializing output $\vec{O}(1)$ and uses six auxiliary power load features as input data (input dimension $v = 30 \times 6$). The outputs are predictions of oil temperature for the subsequent 30 days (output dimension $\mu = 30$).

Contemporary time-series forecasting methods can be categorized into two primary paradigms: classical statistical methods (non-neural network-based) and neural network (NN)-based approaches, with the latter having witnessed rapid advancements in recent years.

For model training, validation, and testing, a total of 666 valid samples were extracted from the ETTm1 dataset. To ensure the fairness of inter-model comparisons, a fixed data partitioning strategy was adopted: a single random permutation of the sample indices was generated using $RI = \text{randperm}(666)$ and retained for all experiments. Among the 666 samples, 400 were allocated for training, with the remaining being used

Fig. 7. (a) Elapsed training time (in Seconds) vs. T ; (b) Elapsed Inference Time (in Seconds) vs. T .

Fig. 8. Comparison of oil temperature prediction performance between RNN and FRNN across six diverse samples. Each subfigure presents the measured oil temperature values (ground truth) alongside the predicted values generated by the RNN and FRNN models. The FRNN predictions consistently exhibit closer alignment with the measured data, demonstrating its superior predictive accuracy for oil temperature forecasting compared to the conventional RNN.

Table 3
Comparison of mean squared error between RNN and FRNN for different application scenarios.

Application Scenario	$E_{MSE}(T)$ (RNN)	$E_{MSE}(T)$ (FRNN)
Oil temperature ($T = 6$)	0.0054	0.0036
Weather ($T = 3$)	0.0062	0.0035
Household Expenses	0.002770	0.002437

for validation and testing. The mini-batch size was set to 24, resulting in a total of $N_b = 20$ mini-batches per training epoch.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed incommensurate FRNN, comparative experiments were conducted against RNN models with

analogous structural configurations. This experimental design ensures that any performance discrepancies can be attributed to the core fractional-order design of the proposed model rather than structural differences between the networks. For a fair and rigorous comparison, both models were initialized with the same parameter settings and trained using identical learning hyperparameters.

In Fig. 8, we demonstrate the oil temperature prediction results of the FRNN in comparison with the RNN across various samples. As observed, the predicted values generated by the FRNN exhibit a closer alignment with the measured temperature data than those produced by the RNN. The total mean squared error (MSE), denoted as E_{MSE} , is further reported in Table 3. Consistent with the visual observations in the figure, this table quantitatively confirms that the E_{MSE} values of the FRNN

Fig. 9. Comparison of weather temperature prediction performance between RNN and incommensurate FRNN. (a)–(e) Temperature prediction results for five representative samples, where each subfigure presents the measured temperature (ground truth) alongside predictions from the RNN and FRNN models. The FRNN predictions consistently demonstrate closer alignment with the measured data, visually confirming its superior predictive accuracy. (f) Evolution of total MSE versus training epochs for both models. The FRNN exhibits faster convergence and achieves a lower final MSE compared to the RNN, quantitatively validating its superior training stability and predictive performance for weather temperature forecasting.

are significantly lower than those of the RNN, verifying the superior predictive performance of the proposed fractional-order model.

9.2. Weather

Daily weather data for Ambaganctg City, Bangladesh, spanning the period from January 1, 2008, to December 31, 2009, were utilized in this study [30]. The dataset is publicly available via Mendeley Data.² For model training and prediction, the previous 10 days of daily temperature data were used to initialize the output vector $\vec{O}(1)$, while three auxiliary features—Month, Sunshine, and Humidity—served as input variables, resulting in an input dimension of $v = 10 \times 3$. All data were normalized to the range $[0, 1]$ to enhance model convergence. The model outputs consisted of temperature predictions for the subsequent 10 days, corresponding to an output dimension of $\mu = 10$.

Fig. 9 presents a comparative analysis of temperature prediction performance between the recurrent neural network (RNN) and the incommensurate fractional recurrent neural network (FRNN). Subgraphs (a)–(e) illustrate prediction results for selected representative samples, where the superiority of the FRNN over the RNN is visually evident. This observation is quantitatively supported by the total mean squared error (MSE) values reported in Table 3, which confirm that the FRNN achieves a lower total MSE than the RNN, further validating its superior predictive accuracy for weather temperature forecasting. For the last scenario, we used household data.³

10. Conclusion

This paper presents a novel architecture for Fractional Recurrent Neural Networks (FRNNs), built upon the framework of Incommensurate Fractional Difference Systems (IFDSs). To address the inherent challenge of back-propagation infeasibility—caused by cross-layer and cross-time parameter coupling—we propose a recursive forward-forward propagation method for gradient computation.

We employ a mini-batch SGD-ADAM optimization strategy, which enables stable and effective tuning of all model parameters, including the memory-controlling fractional order vector $\vec{\alpha}$. Notably, the relative ordering of $\vec{\alpha}$ is preserved throughout training, indicating structural consistency in memory dynamics.

The FRNN is validated on time-series prediction tasks using sinusoidal data that mimic daily temperature patterns. Experimental results demonstrate that optimizing the terminal time step T significantly reduces mean squared error (MSE), confirming the model's ability to capture long-range temporal dependencies.

Further numerical experiments highlight the importance of the fractional memory parameter $\vec{\alpha}$, which plays a crucial role in enhancing prediction accuracy by effectively reducing the system's total energy.

Future research directions include:

- Conducting systematic hyperparameter optimization, including learning rates, batch sizes, and layer widths.
- Investigating theoretical properties such as stability, convergence, and robustness of FRNNs.
- Integrating FRNNs with external memory modules or attention mechanisms for tasks requiring deeper contextual reasoning.

In summary, FRNNs offer a principled and powerful extension to traditional RNNs by incorporating memory decay and long-range dependency modeling. This architecture holds significant promise for time-sensitive and history-dependent learning tasks.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Babak Shiri: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal

analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zahra Alijani:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Ioannis Dassios:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Conceptualization. **Dumitru Baleanu:** Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The MATLAB program is available in <https://github.com/BabakShiri/MATLAB-FRNN>.

References

- [1] A. Abbes, A. Ouannas, N. Shawagfeh, An incommensurate fractional discrete macroeconomic system: bifurcation, chaos, and complexity, *Chin. Phys. B* 32 (2023) 030203.
- [2] A. Al-Husban, N. Djenina, R. Saadeh, A. Ouannas, G. Grassi, A new incommensurate fractional-order covid-19: modelling and dynamical analysis, *Mathematics* 11 (2023) 555.
- [3] H. Al-Taani, M.M. Abu Hammad, M. Abudayah, L. Diabi, A. Ouannas, On fractional discrete memristive model with incommensurate orders: symmetry, asymmetry, hidden chaos and control approaches, *Symmetry* 17 (2025) 143.
- [4] D. Baleanu, J.J. Nieto, B. Shiri, Gronwall inequality for incommensurate systems of weakly singular integral equations and its application to FDES, *Differ. Integral Equ.* 39 (2026) 1–14.
- [5] O. Brandibur, E. Kaslik, Nonlinear dynamics and chaos in fractional-order neural networks, *Neural Netw* 32 (2012) 245–256.
- [6] O. Brandibur, E. Kaslik, Stability of two-component incommensurate fractional-order systems and applications to the investigation of a Fitzhugh-Nagumo neuronal model, *Math. Methods Appl. Sci.* 41 (2018) 7182–7194.
- [7] H. Calgan, Incommensurate fractional-order analysis of a chaotic system based on interaction between dark matter and dark energy with engineering applications, *Physica A: Stat. Mech. Appl.* 635 (2024) 129490.
- [8] B. Cao, X. Nie, J. Cao, P. Duan, Practical finite-time adaptive neural networks control for incommensurate fractional-order nonlinear systems, *Nonlinear Dyn.* 111 (2023) 4375–4393.
- [9] B.-P. Chen, Y. Chen, G.-Q. Zeng, Q. She, Fractional-order convolutional neural networks with population extremal optimization, *Neurocomputing* 477 (2022) 36–45.
- [10] C. Chen, L. Shen, F. Zou, W. Liu, Towards practical Adam: non-convexity, convergence theory, and mini-batch acceleration, *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 23 (2022) 10411–10457.
- [11] L. Chen, W. Guo, A.M. Lopes, R. Wu, P. Li, L. Yin, State-of-charge estimation for lithium-ion batteries based on incommensurate fractional-order observer, *Commun. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul.* 118 (2023) 107059.
- [12] N. Debbouche, A. Ouannas, G. Grassi, A.B. Al-Hussein, F.R. Tahir, K.M. Saad, H. Jahanshahi, A.A. Aly, Chaos in cancer tumor growth model with commensurate and incommensurate fractional-order derivatives, *Comput. Math. Methods Med.* 2022 (2022) 5227503.
- [13] A. Dokoumetzidis, R. Magin, P. Macheras, A commentary on fractionalization of multi-compartmental models, *J. Pharmacokinet. Pharmacodyn.* 37 (2010) 203–207.
- [14] C.S. Drapaca, Fractional calculus in neuronal electromechanics, *J. Mech. Mater. Struct.* 12 (2017) 35–55.
- [15] P. Gong, Q.L. Han, Practical fixed-time bipartite consensus of nonlinear incommensurate fractional-order multiagent systems in directed signed networks, *SIAM J. Control Optim.* 58 (2020) 3322–3341.
- [16] I. Goodfellow, Y. Bengio, A. Courville, *Deep Learning*, MIT Press, 2016.
- [17] J. Jia, F. Wang, Z. Zeng, Bipartite leader-following synchronization of delayed incommensurate fractional-order memristor-based neural networks under signed digraph via adaptive strategy, *Neurocomputing* 505 (2022) 413–432.
- [18] D.P. Kingma, J. Ba, Adam: a method for stochastic optimization, arXiv preprint Published as a conference paper at ICLR 2015 arXiv:1412.6980, 2014.
- [19] H.C. Mao, Y.L. Feng, X.Q. Wang, Z.H. Yao, Weak signal detection application based on incommensurate fractional-order duffing system, *J. Nonlinear Math. Phys.* 31 (2024) 33.

² <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/tbrhznpgw9/1>.

³ <https://opjak.cz/en/>.

- [20] V. Molek, Z. Alijani, Fractional concepts in neural networks: enhancing activation functions, *Pattern Recognit. Lett.* 190 (2025) 126–132.
- [21] J. Ramadoss, S. Aghababaei, F. Parastesh, K. Rajagopal, S. Jafari, I. Hussain, Chimera state in the network of fractional-order fitzhugh–nagumo neurons, *Complexity* 2021 (2021) 2437737.
- [22] S.J. Reddi, S. Kale, S. Kumar, On the convergence of Adam and beyond, in: *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2018.
- [23] M.T. Shatnawi, N. Djenina, A. Ouannas, I.M. Batiha, G. Grassi, Novel convenient conditions for the stability of nonlinear incommensurate fractional-order difference systems, *Alex. Eng. J.* 61 (2022) 1655–1663.
- [24] D. Sheng, Y. Wei, Y. Chen, Y. Wang, Convolutional neural networks with fractional order gradient method, *Neurocomputing* 408 (2020) 42–50.
- [25] B. Shiri, Well-posedness of the mild solutions for incommensurate systems of delay fractional differential equations, *Fract. Fract.* 9 (2025) 60.
- [26] B. Shiri, Y.G. Shi, D. Baleanu, The well-posedness of incommensurate fdes in the space of continuous functions, *Symmetry* 16 (2024) 1058.
- [27] B. Shiri, Y.G. Shi, D. Baleanu, Ulam-Hyers stability of incommensurate systems for weakly singular integral equations, *J. Comput. Appl. Math.* 474 (2025) 116920.
- [28] M. Zaheer, S. Reddi, D. Sachan, S. Kale, S. Kumar, Adaptive methods for nonconvex optimization, in: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2018.
- [29] H. Zhou, S. Zhang, J. Peng, S. Zhang, J. Li, H. Xiong, W. Zhang, Informer: beyond efficient transformer for long sequence time-series forecasting, *Proc. AAAI Conf. Artif. Intell.* 35 (2021) 11106–11115.
- [30] M. Zubair, S. Ahmed, A. Dey, A. Das, M.M. Hasan, An intelligent model to suggest top productive seasonal crops based on user location in the context of Bangladesh, in: *Smart Systems: Innovations in Computing: Proceedings of SSIC 2021*, Springer, 2021, pp. 289–300.

Author biography

Babak Shiri is currently a Professor at the Data Recovery Key Laboratory of Sichuan Province, within the College of Mathematics and Information Science at Neijiang Normal University, Neijiang, China. He holds a Ph.D. in Applied Mathematics (Numerical analysis) from the Faculty of Mathematical Science of the University of Tabriz, Tabriz, Iran, which he completed between 2008 and 2013. His academic research has been published in a variety of prestigious academic journals. His research interests primarily focus on fractional differential equations, integral-algebraic equations, and fuzzy theory.

Zahra Alijani earned her Ph.D. in Applied Mathematics from the University of Tartu, Estonia, in 2021. Presently, she works as a researcher at the Institute for Research and Applications of Fuzzy Modeling at the University of Ostrava in the Czech Republic. Her areas of interest encompass differential equations, soft computing, numerical analysis, and machine learning.

Ioannis Dassios is an Assistant Professor at the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece. He obtained his Ph.D. in Mathematics from the University of Athens in 2013. His research interests include dynamical and control systems, eigenvalue problems, dynamical networks, differential and difference equations, singular systems, fractional calculus, optimization techniques, machine learning, and the mathematical modelling of engineering systems such as power systems, gas networks, and materials science. He has held academic and research positions at University College Dublin, the University of Manchester, the University of Edinburgh, and the University of Limerick. He is the author of more than 110 journal articles, two books, and four edited volumes, and serves on the editorial boards of several international journals. He has reviewed more than 1100 manuscripts, delivered numerous invited talks, and acted as Guest Editor for more than 15 special issues.

Dumitru Baleanu is a Professor at the Department of Computer Science and Mathematics, Lebanese American University, Beirut, Lebanon. Dumitru Baleanu got his PhD from the Institute of Atomic Physics in 1996. His fields of interest include fractional dynamics and its applications, fractional differential equations and their applications, discrete mathematics, image processing, bio-informatics, mathematical biology, mathematical physics, soliton theory, Lie symmetry, dynamic systems on time scales, computational complexity, the wavelet method and its applications, quantization of systems with constraints, the Hamilton-Jacobi formalism, geometries admitting generic and non-generic symmetries. Dumitru Baleanu is co-author of more than 25 books published by Springer, Elsevier and World Scientific. Dumitru Baleanu is a member of several editorial boards of journals indexed in SCI.